

Project ELIXIRxNextGenIT

“ELIXIR x NextGenerationIT: consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure for Omics Data and Bioinformatics”

Area ESFRI “Health and Food”, financed by European Commission – NextGenerationEU

Codice N° IR0000010

ANNEX 2 - APPLICATION FORM

SUBSTITUTE DECLARATION OF CERTIFICATION

(ART. 46 DPR 28.12.2000 N. 445)

SUBSTITUTE DECLARATION OF NOTATORY DEED

(ART. 47 DPR 28.12.2000 N. 445)

To the Project Coordinator Dr. **F. De Leo**

Object: **Assignment of NOA**

The undersigned:

Born in: on (date):

Tax Number (if available):

Gender: male female non binary prefer not to say

User status¹:

Place of residence:

City:

Street: n. ZIP Code:

¹ PGR= Postgraduate; PhD= PhD student; RES= Researcher/Postdoc; TEC= Technician; SEN: Senior researcher

Nationality:

Home institution:

Home institution country:

Institution legal status²:

Certified email (if available:)

e-mail Tel

ASKS

to be admitted participating in the call for the award of n. 1 NOA grant for the service/analysis (indicate the service as reported in the [Annex 1](#)). The NOA will involve products or services or facilities offered by:

- CNR IBIOM
- CNR IBSBC
- UNIBA

The NOA will be provided only by remote service.

DECLARES under his/her own responsibility

- to have the academic degree in

issued by the following Institution on (date)

- to be a Post graduate, PhD student, postdoc, researcher, Senior scientist

(chose one of the options)

at (fill with the name of the Institution);

- to have seen and accepted all the rules contained in this notice and ELIXIR-IT terms of use, ELIXIR-IT data and User Access policies;

- to have not suffered any convictions against the public administration with sentences passed in Court;

² UNI= University and Other Higher Education Organisation; RES= Public Research Organisation (including international research organisations); SME= Small and Medium Enterprise; PRV= Private Research Organisations and other Industrial and/or Profit organisation; OTH= Other type of organisation

- that the activities of NA application are in line with scientific interests of the user's Institution.

The undersigned attaches:

- Project proposal;
- Curriculum Vitae;
- Copy of ID document.

The undersigned, aware of the criminal sanctions provided for in case of false declaration, as established by the art. 76 of the Italian Presidential Decree 28.12.2000 n. 445 declares, under its own responsibility, that the above statements are true. Without prejudice to the provisions of art. 76 of the Presidential Decree 28.12.2000 n. 445, if the above checks reveal the untruthfulness of the content of the declaration, the declarant will lose any benefits obtained as a result of the provision issued on the basis of the untruthful declaration.

The processing of personal data required by this announcement is aimed exclusively at all activities related to the selection and it is pursuant to art.13 of EU Regulation 2016/679 – General Data Protection Regulation.

Place and date

(Signature)

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